

Optimizing Crop Recommendation Systems Using Machine Learning Algorithms

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Abstract— Agriculture remains a vital sector, providing essential sustenance and livelihoods worldwide. However, selecting the optimal crops for specific fields remains a significant challenge, impacting both yields and income. The decline in land fertility exacerbates this issue, necessitating innovative solutions for crop recommendation. This study explores the integration of advanced technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), to enhance crop recommendation systems. Specifically, it focuses on developing a smart crop recommendation model using optimization algorithms such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Shuffled Frog-Leaping Algorithm (SFLA) to optimize Support Vector Machines (SVM). The model aims to predict suitable crops based on soil properties like pH, humidity, temperature, and nutrient levels (N, P, K). Extensive literature review highlights various ML approaches previously employed, underscoring the necessity for more comprehensive and accurate systems. Data for this study was sourced from the Crop Recommendation Dataset on Kaggle. The dataset underwent preprocessing to enhance its quality and facilitate effective model training. The study employed SVMs for initial model training, followed by optimization using PSO and SFLA. Performance metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, and F1 score were utilized to evaluate the models. Post-optimization results demonstrated significant improvements, with PSO achieving an accuracy of 98.64% and SFLA 97.27%, indicating the potential of these approaches in revolutionizing crop recommendation systems. Future recommendations include leveraging advanced ML techniques like deep learning and reinforcement learning to enhance crop recommendation further.

Keywords— Optimization, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Smart Farming

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture serves as the backbone of every economy, providing sustenance and livelihoods for millions. However, farmers grapple with the challenge of selecting optimal crops for their fields, impacting yields and income. Agriculture is associated with producing essential food crops and industrial raw materials. Nonetheless, the capacity to produce food using unfavorable environments and limited agricultural land is critical for the development cycle of a country (Goldstein et al., 2017).

Experts believe that land fertility has diminished over time, thereby affecting crop production levels (Van Klompenburg et al., 2020). Although there is a variety of crops available, concerns have been raised regarding the quality of crops,

productivity, and yield forecast for the future of agriculture (Rezk et al., 2021). It is widely acknowledged that soil type

plays a crucial role in enhancing crop growth and overall agricultural sustainability. However, the conventional agricultural system has long been hampered by a lack of intelligent recommendations. Consequently, agricultural systems often rely on general guidelines, historical knowledge, and limited experimentation (Khan et al., 2021). Such traditional approaches fail to consider the specific needs of individual crops and fields, resulting in inefficient resource allocation, increased costs for farmers, and sub-optimal environmental outcomes (Chen et al., 2019).

To address these challenges, there is a pressing need to revolutionize farming practices. Smart farming has emerged as a solution. Smart farming emerges as a solution, leveraging data on soil conditions, crop yields, and various factors to empower farmers with informed decisions. Smart farming entails using advanced technology, artificial intelligence, and data-driven techniques to optimize agricultural practices. The application of digital technology in agriculture has reduced the need for manual labor, leading to increased productivity, improved living standards, and more people working in the field (Ansari et al., 2022).

The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) and AI in agriculture has witnessed significant growth, reshaping how data is collected, processed, and utilized in real time. AI and machine learning (ML) applications in smart farming focus on various aspects such as crop water management, pest control, and nutrient management. ML recommends suitable crops using various mathematical or statistical methods. By employing these methods, farmers can be advised on the most suitable crop to grow in their particular agricultural region, thereby helping them maximize profits.

This research aims to develop a smart crop recommendation model using state-of-the-art optimizing algorithms such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Shuffled Frog-Leaping Algorithm (SFLA). These algorithms will be used to optimize Support Vector Machines (SVM) and evaluated based on accuracy, sensitivity, precision, specificity, ROC-AUC, and confusion matrix. The goal is to identify the most effective approach for enhancing crop recommendation.

The recommendation of crops depends on various parameters, with the prediction of soil properties being a crucial phase in farming. Soil properties such as pH, humidity, temperature, nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) are directly

related to the geographical and climatic conditions of the area being utilized.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have explored the development of intelligent crop recommendation systems using machine learning (ML) techniques to assist farmers in making informed decisions.

Priyadharshini et al. (2021) proposed an intelligent crop recommendation system utilizing neural networks, achieving an accuracy of 89.88%. While this approach successfully predicted suitable crops, it lacked an in-depth analysis of crop rotation. The study emphasized the importance of considering variables such as soil type, sowing season, and geographic location for effective crop selection. Similarly, Kalimuthu et al. (2020) applied the Naive Bayes algorithm, incorporating soil temperature, humidity, and moisture as crucial variables for crop recommendation. Their research aimed to guide beginner farmers in selecting suitable crops using ML techniques, specifically the supervised learning method of Naive Bayes.

Mariappan et al. (2020) proposed an ML approach utilizing the k-nearest neighbor (KNN) algorithm to analyze soil properties and recommend crops for cultivation. However, their prediction model solely relied on soil properties, neglecting other influential factors. Pudumalar et al. (2015) introduced a recommendation system employing an ensemble model with majority voting technique, incorporating various ML algorithms such as Random Tree, CHAID, K-Nearest Neighbor, and Naive Bayes. This approach aimed to recommend crops based on site-specific parameters with high accuracy and efficiency.

Furthermore, Kumar et al. (2015) proposed a Crop Selection Method (CSM) to maximize the net yield rate of crops and achieve economic growth. Reddy et al. (2019) developed a crop recommendation system based on soil characteristics, utilizing ensemble models and majoritarian voting methods like K-nearest neighbor and Naive Bayes. Suchithra and Pai (2020) utilized extreme learning machines (ELM) to optimize agriculture practices through soil testing and classification. Chambers (2021) explored the impact of ML models on soil property predictions, highlighting the effectiveness of Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Wu et al. (2020) demonstrated the effectiveness of the Generalized Regression Neural Network (GRNN) model in estimating soil nutrients for specific plant communities. Thilakarathne et al. (2022) discussed AI-driven precision agriculture, testing various ML methods like Extreme Gradient Boosting, Decision Tree, Random Forest, KNN, and SVM for crop recommendation.

Rose et al. (2018) emphasized the role of ML classifiers in predicting soil fertility and ecosystem regulation. Rajamanickam (2021) and Rajamanickam and Mani (2021) employed Decision Trees, KNN, and SVM algorithms for predicting soil fertility and addressing environmental challenges in agriculture practices. Katarya et al. (2020) introduced AI techniques, including KNN, similarity-based classifiers, ensemble learning, and neural networks, for crop recommendation based on external factors such as meteorological data and soil profile. Additionally, Kulkarni et al. (2018) proposed a technique utilizing ML algorithms like

linear SVM, Random Forest, and Naive Bayes for accurate crop recommendation based on soil characteristics. Garanayak et al. (2021) compared multiple ML algorithms to determine recommended crop yield, highlighting improvements in agronomic decision-making.

Overall, these studies collectively contribute to the advancement of crop recommendation systems, offering insights into the utilization of ML techniques to enhance agricultural practices and improve crop yields.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section details the materials and methods used in developing a smart crop recommendation model, as depicted in Figure 1. The process begins with the collection of a dataset pertinent to crop recommendations. The collected data undergoes preprocessing to ensure quality and enhance the training process's effectiveness. This preprocessed data is then used to train a machine learning model. The training process is iterative, continuing until the error between actual and predicted values is minimized to an acceptable level. Optimization algorithms are then applied to achieve the best accuracy. The entire implementation is conducted using the machine learning toolbox in Google Colaboratory, with the inclusion of libraries such as pandas, numpy, and sklearn. A comparative analysis is performed to validate the methodology, identifying the most suitable algorithm for crop recommendation.

3.1 Data Collection

The dataset for this study was sourced from the Crop Recommendation Dataset available on Kaggle. It contains 2200 entries and 7 columns, which include N (Nitrogen), P (Phosphorus), K (Potassium), Temperature, Humidity, pH, and Rainfall. This dataset was selected because it encompasses crucial parameters for crop suggestions, such as temperature, humidity, rainfall, pH, and the nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium ratios. These values are specific to each crop.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

After data collection, preprocessing is necessary to prepare it for training. The dataset primarily contains numerical values and has no missing data, thus eliminating the need for handling missing values or encoding categorical variables. Instead, feature selection is performed to identify the most influential features that significantly enhance the model's predictive capability. The dataset is then divided into training, testing, and validation sets to evaluate the model's performance effectively, facilitating robust model training and assessment.

3.3 Training and Optimization

The dataset was trained using SVM, and optimized using Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Shuffled Frog-Leaping Algorithm (SFLA) to learn patterns and relationships in the data and make recommendations on the target variable.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

After applying Support Vector Machines on the crop recommendation dataset, we checked how well the model performed using different measures. Accuracy tells us how often the model's predictions were right compared to all predictions made. Precision focuses on how many of the predicted positives were correct, helping to avoid falsely guessing something is positive when it's not. Recall looks at how good the model is at finding all the actual positives. The F1 score gives a balanced view of precision and recall. Following model training, the results shown in Table 1 were obtained.

Table 1: Training Reports of the models

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Specificity	F1 score
Support Vector Machines	96.13%	0.9627	0.9628	0.9634	0.9606

After Optimization using Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Shuffled Frog-Leaping Algorithm (SFLA). Following model optimization, the results shown in Table 2 were obtained.

Optimization Algorithms	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Specificity	F1 score
Shuffled Frog-Leaping Algorithm	97.27%	0.9734	0.9735	1.0	0.9714
Particle Swarm Optimization	98.64%	0.9880	0.9828	1.0	0.9835

The confusion matrix serves as a crucial tool for evaluating how effectively the model categorizes instances into their respective classes. Below, Figure 4 to Figure 5 display the confusion matrix of two optimization models, providing a detailed insight into the model's classification performance

Figure 4: Confusion Matrix for SFLA

Figure 5: Confusion Matrix for PSO

Lastly, the Area under the ROC Curve (AUC-ROC) served as a performance metric to evaluate the model's ability to differentiate between classes. A higher AUC-ROC value signifies superior discrimination ability of the model. Figure 6 and 7 depicts the ROC curve for the PSO and SFLA.

Figure 6: ROC Curve for PSO

Figure 7: ROC Curve for SFLA

4.2 DISCUSSION

The findings from the study reveal that the optimization of Support Vector Machines with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) outperformed the optimization of Support Vector Machines with Shuffled Frog-Leaping Algorithm (SFLA) in terms of accuracy. Following this, the Support Vector Machine on its own exhibited an accuracy of 96.13%, while with PSO optimization, it reached 98.64%, and with SFLA optimization, it reached 97.27%. Moreover, PSO showed better results across other key metrics like precision, recall, F1 score, specificity and confusion matrix compared to SFLA

5. CONCLUSION

The research explored how machine learning techniques can improve crop recommendations in agriculture. Traditional farming methods often rely on general guidelines, leading to less efficient use of resources and lower crop yields. By using machine learning models like Support Vector Machines and optimizing them with algorithms such as Particle Swarm Optimization and the Shuffled Frog-Leaping Algorithm, the study demonstrated significant improvements in crop recommendation accuracy.

The findings highlight the importance of using data-driven approaches in agriculture. PSO performed better than SFLA across various metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and specificity. Further analysis using confusion matrices confirmed PSO's superiority, with more true positives and true negatives, and fewer false positives and false negatives compared to SFLA.

The enhanced accuracy and performance metrics observed in this study highlight the potential benefits of incorporating modern technology to tackle longstanding agricultural obstacles. Through harnessing comprehensive data on soil characteristics, meteorological conditions, and other environmental variables, farmers are empowered to make well-informed decisions, thus fostering advancements that positively impact the agricultural domain as a whole.

6. CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

Optimizing SVM models for crop recommendation using PSO and SFLA is an innovative approach. The research demonstrates that these optimization techniques can significantly enhance the accuracy of crop predictions, helping farmers make more informed decisions about crop selection. The findings underscore the effectiveness of integrating ML models with optimization algorithms and suggest further exploration of advanced techniques such as deep learning and reinforcement learning. This opens avenues for future research to further refine agricultural recommendations. By addressing the challenge of optimal crop selection, the study provides practical solutions for farmers, potentially leading to increased yields and income. This contribution is particularly important in the context of declining land fertility and the need for sustainable agricultural practices.

6. RECOMMENDATION

Future research works should adopt more advanced models that utilize ML models and optimization algorithms to improve crop selection and overall agricultural productivity. Governments and private sectors should invest in the research and development of advanced agricultural technologies. This includes funding for developing new ML models and optimization techniques tailored to specific crop types and regional conditions.

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